

The Reaction between Molybdic Acid and Diphenylcarbazide*

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Diphenylcarbazide (HDPI) reduces molybdic acid in acetone-HCl solution to provide pentavalent molybdenum which forms violet complexes with diphenylcarbazide and/or diphenylcarbazone (HDPO). Two solid complexes of pentavalent molybdenum, represented by the formulas $[(DPI)(DPO)OMo-O-Mo(DPO)(DPI)]^o$ (I) and $[(DPO)_2OMo-O-MoO(DPO)_2]^o$ have been isolated. Both the compounds behave like non-electrolytes, but compound (II) is insoluble in benzene. It has low magnetic moment, whereas compound (I) is diamagnetic. The spectra of both the compounds in acetone solution show intense absorption maxima in the region of 520-540 m μ , which are due to charge-transfer transitions.

Diphenylcarbazide ($C_6H_5NH.NH.CO:NH.NHC_6H_5$) exhibits colour reactions with many metal ions and is a sensitive analytical reagent for chromium(VI)¹. It reacts with molybdenum(VI) to produce a red-violet colour^{2,3}. Feigl⁴ has observed that diphenylcarbazone, formed by the oxidation of diphenylcarbazide, reacts with molybdate in some unexplained manner to produce the colour. In an earlier paper⁵, the present authors have reported that diphenylcarbazone reacts with molybdic acid to yield a violet-coloured compound of composition $[MoO_2(DPO)_2]^o$ (where DPO represents a molecule of diphenylcarbazone less one hydrogen atom). In the present investigation, the reaction between molybdic acid and diphenylcarbazide has been studied by physico-chemical methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

Most of the chemicals used were of A.R. quality. Benzene, acetone, and acetic acid were purified before use. Molybdenum content in molybdic acid was checked by lead molybdate method. The strength of hydrochloric and sulphuric acids was determined by titration with a standard borax solution using Methyl red as an indicator. Diphenylcarbazide was purified by recrystallisation from hot ethanol. Pure diphenylcarbazide ($99.4 \pm 0.3\%$), m.p. 173°, was obtained by drying the product under vacuum. The purity of diphenylcarbazide was determined by the method of Ghosh and Ray⁶, using potentiometric end point. Radiometer type PHM 22r (No. 45158) was employed for all potentiometric titrations. Spectrophotometric measurements were taken on a Unicam SP 500 (No. 23481)

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4. Feigl, "Spot Tests", Vol. I, 4th ed., 1954, p. 114.
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spectrophotometer. Fused silica cells of 1 cm optical path were employed. Gouy's balance, as described by Prasad *et al.*⁷, was used for magnetic measurements.

Preparation of the Compounds.—10 *N*-HCl (30ml) containing 1.3 g. of molybdic acid was kept in an ice bath for 15 min. About 4 g. of pure diphenylcarbazide in 60 ml of acetone was added with constant stirring to molybdic acid solution. The mixture was diluted with 200 ml of water and kept for 24 hr. at the room temperature. The solid was separated, washed with water till free of molybdenum and chloride, and dried over H₂SO₄ (conc.). It was then dissolved in benzene and filtered to remove the insoluble residue. On evaporating the benzene solution, the solid compound (I) was obtained. The benzene-insoluble residue was repeatedly washed with benzene and was then dissolved in acetone. A deep blue powder (II) was collected after removing acetone at the room temperature.

Molybdenum in compounds(I) and(II) was estimated by lead molybdate method. The valency of molybdenum and the number of DPO and DPI groups (where DPI represents a molecule of diphenylcarbazide less one hydrogen atom) in compounds (I) and (II) were arrived at by treating the solution of the compounds with a ferric alum solution and determining the amount of reduced ferrous ions produced by potentiometric titration with a standard potassium dichromate solution.

A known amount of compound (I) was dissolved in minimum quantity of acetone and the violet colour was destroyed with a known volume of standard sulphuric acid solution. The yellow-coloured solution was diluted with water so that the final strength of sulphuric acid was 0.2*N*. An equimolecular solution of potassium dichromate was prepared by dissolving potassium dichromate in 0.2*N*-H₂SO₄.

Absorption measurements of the mixture solutions were taken at 500 m μ and 540 m μ because at these wave lengths absorptions due to the reactants were negligible.

DISCUSSION

The spectral curves of molybdic acid and diphenylcarbazide, mixed in the proportion of 1:2 in acetone-hydrochloric acid mixture, are shown in Fig. 1 and 2. The absorption peak between 430 m μ and 460 m μ may be assigned to pentavalent molybdenum formed by the reduction of molybdic acid with diphenylcarbazide. The presence of pentavalent molybdenum in the solution is also indicated by the thiocyanate test. Other reducing agents⁸⁻¹² in HCl solution less than 4 *N* are known to produce pentavalent molybdenum which exists in dimeric form and shows maximum absorption in the range 395-460m μ . In solutions of higher acidities it changes into monomeric form and shows absorption maximum at 720 m μ . With diphenylcarbazide as a reducing agent, the peak at 720 m μ is not observed even in 6-8*N* hydrochloric acid solution because the formation of monomeric pentavalent

7. Prasad *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1944, **20A**, 224.

8. Foerster and Fricke, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1923, **36**, 458.

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10. Hiakay and Meloche, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 1819.

11. EL-Shamy and EL-Aggan, *ibid.*, 1953, **75**, 1187.

12. Height (Jr.), *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, **24**, 663.

molybdenum is most probably hindered by presence of acetone. The absorption peak at $540\text{ m}\mu$, which appears in $0.025\text{--}0.1N\text{-HCl}$ solution, is due to the complexes of pentavalent molybdenum with diphenylcarbazide and/or diphenylcarbazone, the oxidation product of diphenylcarbazide. In $0.025N$ hydrochloric acid solution, the peak at $460\text{ m}\mu$ is initially more intense than the peak at $540\text{ m}\mu$. With increasing time, the maxima at $540\text{ m}\mu$ becomes more intense and that at $460\text{ m}\mu$ disappears (Fig. 3). This indicates that the reduction of molybdic acid precedes complex formation.

FIG. 1. Spectral curves of molybdic acid and diphenylcarbazide in HCl solutions.

Curve 1 : $M/6000\text{-H}_2\text{MoO}_4$ and $M/3000\text{-HDPI}$ in $8N\text{-HCl}$.

Curve 2 : $M/2400\text{-H}_2\text{MoO}_4$ and $M/1200\text{-HDPI}$ in $6N\text{-HCl}$.

Curve 3 : $M/800\text{-H}_2\text{MoO}_4$ and $M/400\text{-HDPI}$ in $4N\text{-HCl}$.

Curve 4 : $M/1000\text{-H}_2\text{MoO}_4$ and $M/500\text{-HDPI}$ in $2N\text{-HCl}$.

Curve 5 : $M/600\text{-H}_2\text{MoO}_4$ and $M/300\text{-HDPI}$ in $1N\text{-HCl}$.

Two solid compounds, insoluble in water and sparingly soluble in ethanol, chloroform etc., have been isolated. But compound (I) is soluble in benzene (3.911 g./litre at 35°), whereas compound (II) is not so. Both the compounds in HCl-acetone mixture respond to tests for pentavalent molybdenum with thiocyanate, but only compound (I) shows test for diphenylcarbazide with potassium dichromate.

Compound (I): (Found : Mo, 15.85; N, 18.50. $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7\cdot\text{C}_{52}\text{H}_{48}\text{N}_{16}$ requires Mo, 15.93; N, 18.66%).

Compound (II): (Found: Mo, 15.92; N, 18.60. $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7\cdot\text{C}_{52}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_{16}$ requires Mo, 15.98; N, 18.73%).

Compounds (I) and (II) reduce seven and five equivalents respectively of ferric ions per g. atom of molybdenum in the compound. The above results suggest that compounds (I) and (II) may be represented by the dimeric formulas as:

(I)

(II)

FIG. 2: Spectral curves of molybdic acid and diphenylcarbazide in HCl solutions. Strength of molybdic acid solution = $M/2250$; diphenylcarbazide solution = $M/1125$.

Curve 1 : 0.1N-HCl.

Curve 2 : 0.05N-HCl.

Curve 3 : 0.025 N-HCl.

Because of the low solubility of the compounds in organic solvents, molecular weights could not be determined. It is not possible to determine oxygen directly and oxygen is included to give overall charge neutrality for pentavalent molybdenum, consistent with the analysis.

Additional evidence in favour of the above formula for compound (I) has been obtained from the study of the reaction between decolorised solution of compound (I) and potassium dichromate solution by Job's continued variation method. With equimolar solutions, the maximum in Jobs' curves occurs at the point of complex: dichromate = 1:1. In the mole-ratio method, the break in the curve also appears at the ratio of complex: dichromate = 1:1. The formation of the violet colour may be explained on the basis of the following reactions.

The reaction (d) may or may not take place, depending on the acidity and acetone content of the solution.

FIG. 3. Spectral curves of molybdic acid and diphenylcarbazide in 0.025N-HCl with time. Strength of molybdic acid solution = $M/2250$ and that of diphenylcarbazide solution = $M/1125$. Curve 1 : 25 hr. Curve 2 : 71 hr. Curve 3: 116 hr. Curve 4: 166 hr. Curve 5: 234 hr.

The unit Mo_2O_3 , which has been reported to occur in other complexes of pentavalent molybdenum, contains a single oxide bridge¹⁵. Since in acid solution both diphenylcarbazide and diphenylcarbazone are expected to react in keto-form, the following structures may be tentatively assigned to compounds (I) and (II).

The formulations shown below explain the magnetic properties of the compounds (I) (diamagnetic) and (II) ($\mu_{\text{corr.}} = 1.0830 \text{ B.M.}$) because oxygen bridge in oxo-complexes of metals leads to a large reduction of magnetic susceptibility¹⁶. However, low paramagnetism

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14. Pfau and Howick, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 4882.

15. Mitchell, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1953, **25**, 983.

16. Earnshaw and Lewis, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 396.

of compound (II) and diamagnetism of compound (I) may also be due to direct spin-spin interaction in the solid state, and chelate ring may be formed through nitrogen instead of through oxygen.

Compound (I)

FIG. 4 : Spectral curves of compounds (I) and (II) in acetone.
 Curve 1 : $2.798 \times 10^{-4}M$ compound (I) in acetone. Curve 2 : $1.089 \times 10^{-4}M$ compound (II) in acetone.
 Curve 3 : Spectral curve of solution obtained by discharging the violet colour of acetone solution with 2N HCl.

Compound (II)

Both the compounds in acetone show intense absorption maxima in the range 530 m μ -540 m μ , which are due to charge-transfer transitions⁵. Absorption maxima in the region 420-460 m μ due to molybdenum (ν) are masked by the strong-charge-transfer band. When the violet colour of the acetone solution is discharged by the addition of hydrochloric acid, maximum absorption at 420 m μ is observed (Fig. 4, curve 3).

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